

**Open Science in the
Czech Republic: Potential,
Barriers and Directions
for Further Development**

English Extended Summary

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Open Science in the Czech Republic: Potential, Barriers and Directions for Further Development

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Purpose and scope of the study

This extended summary presents the main findings and recommendations of the Czech-language study *Open Science in the Czech Republic: Potential, Barriers and Directions for Further Development*. The study assesses the current state of Open Science and FAIR research data management in the Czech Republic and identifies the main barriers, opportunities and directions for further development, with particular attention to the period after 2028.

Although the full report focuses primarily on the Czech national context, many of its findings are relevant to other countries and research systems facing similar challenges: the transition from project-based development to long-term institutionalisation, the sustainability of Open Science services and infrastructures, the development of data stewardship and expert support capacities, the role of research assessment, and the cost dynamics of Open Access publishing.

The study was prepared within the project [‘Strategic Intelligence for Research and Innovation’ \(STRATIN+\): MS25001](#), supported by the [Ministry of Education, Youth and Sports of the Czech Republic \(MEYS, MŠMT in Czech\)](#). It was developed as an analytical and strategic input for public policy, particularly for actors involved in research, development and innovation governance in the Czech Republic.

Methodological approach

The study is based on a mixed-methods approach combining policy analysis, empirical surveys, qualitative interviews and strategic synthesis. The analysis draws on national and international policy documents, European and global Open Science frameworks, available data and statistics relating to Open Science, Open Access and research data management, as well as empirical evidence from the Czech research environment.

The empirical part of the study includes questionnaire surveys conducted among three key stakeholder groups: researchers, Open Science support professionals and representatives of the management of research organisations. These surveys were complemented by semi-structured interviews with selected key actors, an expert workshop and a panel discussion on the future of Open Science in the Czech Republic. The results were subsequently synthesised through a SWOT analysis, allowing the study to identify major strengths, weaknesses, opportunities and threats across the Czech Open Science ecosystem.

The study focuses especially on Open Access to scholarly publications and FAIR research data management, including the availability of infrastructures, support services, expert capacities and institutional frameworks. It also examines broader enabling conditions, including national coordination, research assessment, research integrity, citizen science, research infrastructures, skills and long-term financing.

Strategic context: why Open Science matters

Open Science and FAIR research data management are presented in the study as a major transformation framework for research systems in Europe and globally. Their importance is expected to grow after 2028 due to several parallel trends: the digitalisation of research, the development of artificial intelligence and data spaces, pressure for more efficient use of

public investment, and growing expectations concerning transparency, reproducibility and research security.

At the European level, Open Science is closely linked to the European Research Area, Horizon Europe, the European Open Science Cloud, reform of research assessment and wider debates on responsible, transparent and trustworthy research. The study emphasises that Open Science should not be understood merely as a set of technical requirements or administrative obligations. Rather, it represents a long-term systemic and institutional transformation affecting research practices, scholarly communication, research data management, research assessment, institutional governance and the relationship between science and society.

For the Czech Republic, Open Science is therefore not only a specialised policy agenda but also a strategic opportunity to increase the quality, efficiency and international competitiveness of research and innovation. If implemented in a coordinated and sustainable way, Open Science can also help reduce administrative burden by harmonising rules, standardising procedures and providing shared services to researchers and institutions.

The Czech Open Science landscape: transition from project-based development to systemic institutionalisation

The Czech Open Science ecosystem has developed significantly in recent years. New infrastructures, methodological tools, support services and institutional initiatives have emerged, particularly in connection with European policy requirements, national projects and the development of EOSC-related activities. These investments have created an important foundation for the implementation of Open Science principles.

At the same time, the study shows that much of this development has so far been driven by time-limited projects. This creates a fundamental sustainability problem. Project funding has been effective in launching new activities, building capacity and testing approaches, but it is not sufficient for the long-term operation of services and infrastructures that researchers and institutions are expected to rely on as part of everyday research practice.

The Czech system is therefore at a critical transition point. It needs to move from project-based and partly fragmented development towards stable, system-wide institutionalisation. The future development of Open Science in the Czech Republic will depend on whether existing initiatives can be stabilised, interconnected and embedded into the regular functioning of the research system.

Key finding 1: implementation is uneven across institutions and disciplines

One of the central findings of the study is that the implementation of Open Science in the Czech Republic remains highly uneven. Significant differences exist between research organisations in terms of available infrastructure, expert support, internal policies and strategic commitment. Some institutions have developed relatively advanced services, internal processes and support teams, while others still operate in a largely ad hoc manner, often relying on motivated individuals or individual departments.

This heterogeneity is visible not only between institutions but also across disciplines and types of research. Different fields have different traditions, data types, publication cultures, legal constraints and levels of readiness for data sharing. These disciplinary differences need to be recognised in policy design. The study therefore does not recommend a simplistic, one-size-fits-all model of openness. Instead, it supports the principle that research outputs should be as open as possible and as closed as necessary, with appropriate attention to legal, ethical, security-related and disciplinary conditions.

The unevenness of implementation is not primarily a technical problem. It reflects deeper differences in institutional capacity, leadership, funding, available expertise and strategic orientation. Without a minimum level of institutional support across the system, Open Science risks becoming a privilege of better-resourced institutions rather than a common standard of responsible research practice.

Key finding 2: Open Science is often perceived as an administrative obligation

The study finds that Open Science is often perceived by researchers as an administrative requirement linked to funder obligations rather than as an integral part of high-quality research. This is particularly visible in relation to data management plans, Open Access requirements and reporting obligations.

This does not mean that researchers reject Open Science as such. The survey among researchers indicates that awareness of Open Science is increasing and that many researchers already apply some Open Science principles in their work. Researchers also recognise potential benefits, such as easier collaboration, greater visibility of research results and improved trustworthiness of research. However, broader adoption is limited by financial, institutional and practical barriers.

The study therefore stresses that implementation should not rely only on formal obligations. If Open Science is experienced primarily as another compliance layer, it may increase administrative burden and produce formalistic implementation with limited real impact. For Open Science to become part of research culture, it must be supported by clear institutional rules, accessible expert services, stable funding and meaningful incentives in research assessment and career development.

Key finding 3: fragmented rules and insufficient coordination reduce system efficiency

A major systemic barrier is the absence of a unified national strategic framework for Open Science. The Czech system currently lacks a shared long-term vision, clearly defined roles, harmonised requirements and a stable coordination mechanism across the main actors of the research and innovation system.

The study identifies fragmentation of rules and requirements as a key practical problem. Different funders and programmes apply different definitions, expectations, reporting rules and approaches to Open Access and research data management. This creates uncertainty for researchers and institutions and increases administrative workload. It also reduces the efficiency of public investment, because services and infrastructures are not always developed within a coordinated national framework.

The study also points to unclear division of responsibilities between the national and institutional levels. Some functions require national coordination and shared infrastructure, while others must be implemented locally within research organisations. The absence of a clear governance model makes it difficult to determine who should finance, operate, monitor and maintain specific components of the Open Science ecosystem.

Key finding 4: Open Access publishing is shaped by cost pressures and dependence on commercial publishers

The study analyses Open Access publishing as one of the most developed but also most economically challenging areas of Open Science. The Czech Republic has built important national capacities for access to electronic information resources and for negotiating transformative agreements, particularly through national-level mechanisms connected to CzechELib and related activities. Many institutions are involved in transformative agreements and use them as a practical mechanism for Open Access publishing.

However, the study also highlights the risks of continued dependence on large commercial publishers. The current publishing system is associated with rising costs, strong market concentration and a close connection between publishing practices and research assessment systems that still rely heavily on bibliometric indicators. This model can reinforce publication pressure and limit the development of more open, diverse and cost-effective forms of scholarly communication.

Institutional approaches to financing publication fees are uneven. Some institutions provide coordinated support, while others rely mainly on project budgets or decentralised arrangements at the level of departments or research teams. Dedicated institutional funds for publication fees are not widespread. Support for Diamond Open Access remains limited, despite its potential to reduce financial barriers for both authors and readers.

The study therefore recommends active cost management, transparent monitoring of publication expenditures, stronger negotiating capacity and diversification of Open Access models, including targeted support for Diamond Open Access and other non-APC-based models where appropriate.

Key finding 5: FAIR research data management requires stronger expert and institutional support

FAIR research data management is one of the most important and demanding areas of Open Science implementation. The study emphasises that FAIR does not mean that all research data must be fully open. Data can be FAIR even when access is restricted for legal, ethical, security-related or commercial reasons, provided that metadata, access conditions and documentation are appropriately managed.

In the Czech Republic, research data management is developing, but it remains uneven and insufficiently supported. Roles such as data stewards or research data management specialists are not yet systematically embedded across the research system. Their availability varies significantly between institutions. In many cases, responsibility for data management still falls mainly on researchers themselves, often without sufficient methodological, legal or technical support.

The study identifies several barriers to better data management and sharing: legal uncertainty, lack of expert support, concerns about misuse of data, insufficient familiarity with FAIR principles, limited use of disciplinary or national repositories and the absence of stable support structures. Researchers express interest in training in FAIR principles, licensing and data management plans, but training alone is not enough. It must be accompanied by institutional services, advisory capacity, technical infrastructure and clear rules.

The development of national and federated infrastructures, including those connected to EOSC, is therefore important. However, infrastructure must be accompanied by sustainable governance, expert staff, interoperability standards and support embedded in research organisations.

Key finding 6: research assessment and career incentives remain weakly aligned with Open Science

The study stresses that Open Science cannot be fully implemented unless it is connected to the way research is assessed, funded and institutionally supported. At present, openness is not sufficiently reflected in research assessment and career progression. This weakens motivation and contributes to the perception that Open Science is an external requirement rather than a recognised component of research quality.

The study does not recommend mechanically equating research quality with the degree of openness of individual outputs. Instead, it argues for a more careful and responsible approach. Assessment should recognise whether institutions create functional conditions for responsible openness: available support, infrastructure, staff capacity, legal and security frameworks, training and appropriate procedures. For research data, software and other relevant outputs, assessment should focus on the quality of management, documentation, transparency and potential for verification or reuse where this is legally and substantively appropriate.

This approach is important because not all outputs can or should be fully open. Responsible Open Science must take into account sensitive data, intellectual property, research security and disciplinary differences. The goal is not openness for its own sake, but better, more transparent, more reliable and more reusable research.

Key finding 7: human capacities and skills are a bottleneck

A recurring finding across the study is the shortage and uneven distribution of expert capacities. Open Science implementation requires a combination of roles and competencies: Open Science coordination, data stewardship, repository management, legal advice, licensing expertise, methodological support, training, IT support and knowledge of disciplinary practices.

Many Czech research organisations already provide some forms of support, especially in Open Access publishing, licensing advice, training and repository-related services. However, the availability and depth of these services differ substantially. Support capacities are often concentrated at the central institutional level, while faculties, institutes, departments or research groups may have much less access to hands-on assistance.

The study therefore recommends defining a minimum institutional standard for Open Science support. This standard should include at least coordination, advisory services, support for

data management planning and data stewardship capacity or equivalent expertise. The standard should be supported by national-level funding and methodological tools so that all research organisations can reach a baseline level of service.

Key finding 8: citizen science and broader public engagement remain underdeveloped

The study includes citizen science as one of the dimensions of Open Science, while recognising that it is less developed in the Czech context than Open Access and research data management. Citizen science has the potential to strengthen public trust in science, support wider societal engagement and open research processes to non-academic actors.

However, its further development requires more systematic support, clearer methodological guidance, suitable funding mechanisms and integration into broader Open Science and research policy frameworks. Citizen science should not be treated as an isolated activity but as part of a wider approach to openness, trust, participation and responsible research.

Key finding 9: research security and responsible openness must be addressed together

The study explicitly addresses the relationship between Open Science and research security. It emphasises the principle of intelligent openness: as open as possible, as closed as necessary. Open Science should not be interpreted as unlimited openness. Legal, ethical, security-related and legitimate economic considerations may justify restrictions on access to certain data, information or research outputs.

This is particularly relevant in an environment where research is increasingly digital, international and data-intensive. Responsible openness requires institutions to be able to identify and manage risks, especially in areas involving sensitive data, dual-use research, personal data, intellectual property, international collaboration and research security. This requires not only rules, but also institutional capacity, expert advice and trusted infrastructure.

The study therefore calls for clearer legal and security guidance so that researchers and institutions can make informed decisions about what can be shared, under what conditions and through which mechanisms.

Main systemic barriers

The study identifies four primary systemic barriers that are particularly important for policymakers and institutional leaders.

The first barrier is the absence of unified strategic management and coordination of Open Science at national level. Without a national strategy, implementation remains fragmented and dependent on individual projects, institutions or motivated actors.

The second barrier is the unsustainability of services and infrastructures that depend on short-term project funding, despite the need for long-term operation. Open Science services such as repositories, data support, national platforms and expert roles require stable, multiannual funding.

The third barrier is insufficient and uneven expert support capacity. This includes data stewardship, legal and methodological support, repository services, Open Access support and other specialised roles needed to make Open Science workable in everyday research practice.

The fourth barrier is the weakness of incentive structures in research assessment and career development. If openness, responsible data management, transparent methods, reusable outputs and related practices are not recognised, they will remain secondary to traditional publication metrics and short-term performance pressures.

Other problems identified in the study, such as formalistic implementation, uneven uptake or limited motivation among some researchers, are largely consequences of these underlying systemic barriers.

Policy and practice recommendations

The study proposes a set of recommendations for public policy and institutional practice.

Prepare a national Open Science strategy for the period after 2028

The Czech Republic should adopt a national Open Science strategy for the post-2028 period. The strategy should define a long-term vision, priorities, concrete objectives, roles of key actors, implementation mechanisms, monitoring procedures and evaluation arrangements. It should provide a common framework for funders, ministries, research organisations, national infrastructures and support communities.

Establish stable multiannual funding for key services and infrastructures

Open Science requires a clear distinction between the investment phase, which may be suitable for project funding, and the operational phase, which requires stable financing. Repositories, national platforms, research data services, data stewardship capacity and other core components should be financed through predictable, multiannual mechanisms.

Define a minimum institutional standard for Open Science support

Each research organisation should provide a minimum level of Open Science support, including coordination, advisory services, support for data management plans, licensing and legal guidance, and data stewardship or equivalent expertise. National-level methodological tools and funding should help institutions meet this standard.

Develop a federated and interoperable infrastructure ecosystem

The Czech Open Science infrastructure ecosystem should combine shared national components with local implementation at the level of research organisations. National components may include persistent identifiers, service catalogues, repository platforms, interoperability frameworks and integration with European initiatives such as EOSC.

Align research assessment with responsible Open Science

Open Science should be reflected in research assessment and career development in a balanced way. Assessment should recognise institutional conditions for responsible openness and the quality of data management, documentation, transparency and reusability where appropriate. It should avoid simplistic metrics that mechanically reward openness without considering quality, context or legitimate restrictions.

Manage Open Access costs and diversify publishing models

The Czech Republic should monitor publication costs more transparently, strengthen national negotiating capacity and support alternative models of Open Access publishing. Special attention should be given to Diamond Open Access and other models that reduce barriers for authors and readers and reduce dependence on commercial publishers.

Strengthen legal and security guidance

Researchers and institutions need clearer guidance on copyright, licensing, secondary publishing rights, data protection, sensitive data, intellectual property and research security. Responsible openness requires legal certainty and support, not only general policy declarations.

Invest in skills and professional roles

Open Science implementation depends on people. The system needs sustainable professional roles, training pathways and communities of practice, particularly in data stewardship, Open Science coordination, repository management, licensing and legal support, and research data management.

Relevance beyond the Czech Republic

Although this study focuses on the Czech Republic, its findings are relevant for other national research systems. Many countries are dealing with similar tensions: how to move from policy declarations to everyday practice; how to fund Open Science services sustainably; how to develop data stewardship capacity; how to avoid excessive administrative burden; how to align Open Science with research assessment; and how to manage the costs and power asymmetries of scholarly publishing.

The Czech case illustrates a broader European and international challenge. Open Science cannot be implemented effectively through isolated projects or compliance requirements alone. It requires coordinated governance, stable funding, institutional capacity, trusted infrastructures, meaningful incentives and careful attention to disciplinary, legal and security contexts.

The key message of the study is therefore clear. Open Science has significant potential to modernise the Czech research system, but this potential will only be realised if the country moves from fragmented and project-based development towards a coordinated, sustainable and institutionally embedded model.

Supplementary materials

The full Czech-language report includes appendices referring to supporting outputs and datasets, including the results of questionnaire surveys among researchers, representatives of research organisation management and Open Science support professionals, as well as materials from the panel discussion, qualitative interviews and workshop, and an analysis of Open Access publishing based on Web of Science data. These supplementary materials provide additional empirical grounding for the findings summarised above.